

NOTES

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC DATA, ELECTRONIC BANDS AND SPECTRAL PARAMETERS (cm⁻¹)

Complex	μ_{eff} B.M.	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	10Dq	B	β	Dq/B	ν_3/ν_1	h_x	f factor
[Ni(en) ₂ (acac)]Cl	2.94	10990	18020	30300	10990	1023	0.97	1.06	1.63	0.25	1.26
[Ni(en) ₂ (MAA)]Cl	3.19	11050	17860	29240	11050	930	0.88	1.18	1.61	1.00	1.27
[Ni(en) ₂ (EAA)]Cl	3.08	10420	16980	28410	10420	942	0.90	1.10	1.63	1.93	1.20
[Ni(pn) ₂ (acac)]Cl	3.20	9670	15870	27550	9570	980	0.93	0.97	1.65	0.58	1.10
[Ni(pn) ₂ (MAA)]Cl	3.01	10530	16180	25510	10530	673	0.64	1.56	1.53	3.00	1.21
[Ni(pn) ₂ (EAA)]Cl	3.10	10100	16000	25970	10100	778	0.74	1.29	1.58	2.17	1.16

TABLE 2—SIGNIFICANT IR BANDS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES

[Ni(en) ₂] Cl ₂	[Ni(en) ₂ (acac)]Cl	[Ni(en) ₂ (MAA)]Cl	[Ni(en) ₂ (EAA)]Cl	[Ni(pn)] Cl ₂	[Ni(pn)] (acac)Cl	[Ni(pn)] (MAA)Cl	[Ni(pn)] (EAA)Cl	Assignments
3410w	—	3420s	—	—	3400sh	—	—	} ν N-H
3320sh	3380w	3310s	3370w	3335w	—	—	—	
3280w	—	—	3280w	3200w	—	3300mbr	3300mbr	} 2(δ NH ₂)
3240w	3240sh	3230w	3240sh	3260w	3240sh	—	—	
2930s	2930m	2960s	2980s	2970s	2980m	2960w	2960w	ν_{as} (C-H)
2870m	2890w	2840w	2980w	2890m	2880m	—	—	ν_s (C-H)
—	1650sh	1650s	1630sh	—	1650w	1680w	1690sh	ν C-O
—	1620w	1620w	1620s	1625w	1630sh	1630m	1620w	ν C-C
1585s	1605w	1585s	1600w	1600s	1610s	1620s	1580w	δ NH ₂
—	1515s	150Cs	1570s	1505vw	1570s	1515sh	1515w	ν_s (C-N) + ν_s (N-H)
1450w	1465w	1470w	—	1460s	1460s	1455m	1455w	CH ₂ and CH ₃ asym. deform.
1270m	1265s	1280s	1250s	1275s	1265s	1265w	—	ν_s (C-N)
—	1205m	1215s	—	1200m	1200s	1200w	1200w	} CH ₂ rock + ν_{as} C-C-C
1140w	1155w	1170s	1175w	1160m	—	1145w	1145w	
1080vs	1035w	1035w	1030w	—	—	—	—	} C-NH ₂
—	1025s	—	—	—	—	—	—	
1015w	1010w	1000w	1015w	1020s	1020s	1020m	1015w	} (C-N) + (N-H)
—	770vw	785s	780s	—	770s	760w	—	
425m	430m	450m	435m	445w	420s	445s	440w	ν (N1-N)

Table 2 indicates all mixed ligand complex show four bands in the range 1690-1500 cm⁻¹. The ν C=C, ν C=N, ν (NH₂) and ν C=O (β -keto compound) stretches are clearly observed in all the complexes. The systematic presence of C=C, C=N and C=O stretches is a necessary condition for the mixed ligand formulation¹¹. However, it is difficult to assign all band in the region 1690-1500 cm⁻¹, only tentative assignment of such ligand system can be given.

Direct evidence for M-O bonding could only be observed at about 440 cm⁻¹ but all the M-O frequencies could not be obtained as M-O falls below the range of the instrument used.

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Synthesis and Spectral Studies of Lanthanide Complexes with Fluoro β -diketones

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LANTHANIDE β -diketonates have been found to have wide applications as pseudocontact nmr shift reagents¹⁻³. Some of these chelates have been used for the chromatographic separation of lanthanides⁴⁻⁵. The paper describes the synthesis of anhydrous chelates of lanthanides with trifluoro, hexafluoro acetyl-acetone, benzoyl trifluoroacetone and pentafluoro benzoyl acetone and characterization of these by magnetic and spectral studies.

Experimental

Diaquo tris chelates of lanthanides with these

fluoro β -diketones have been prepared by the method described earlier⁶.

Preparation of anhydrous chelates: Anhydrous chelates have been prepared by the azeotropic removal of water from the hydrated analogue. The hydrated chelate was refluxed with benzene containing ethanol under a highly efficient fractionating column. The ternary azeotrope consisting of water-benzene-alcohol was fractionated out at a high reflux ratio (~30:1). The amount of water collected in the distillate was estimated. The anhydrous chelate was obtained after removal of solvent under reduced pressure. The product was later purified by recrystallization from refluxing benzene.

Infrared spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on Perkin Elmer 521 spectrophotometer. Absorption spectra of the benzene solution of the chelates have been recorded on Carl Zeiss double beam spectrophotometer.

Lanthanides were estimated by first decomposing the chelate by concentrated nitric acid and evaporating it to dryness. The dried mass was extracted with dil. HCl and the metal was precipitated as oxalate by addition of excess ammonium oxalate.

The analytical data are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Sl. No.	Complex	%M		%C		Mol. wt.	Mol. wt.
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.		
1.	Pr(TFAA) ₃	23.6	23.47	30.2	30.02	1080	1300
2.	Nd(TFAA) ₃	24.0	23.90	30.2	29.85	(1.8)	(2.16)
3.	Sm(TFAA) ₃	24.8	24.66	29.8	29.55		
4.	Ho(TFAA) ₃	26.6	26.42	29.0	28.86		
5.	Er(TFAA) ₃	26.8	26.69	29.0	28.75		
6.	Pr(HFAA) ₃	19.5	18.83	24.8	24.21	1250	1600
7.	Nd(HFAA) ₃	19.5	19.30	24.3	24.10	(1.75)	(2.2)
8.	Sm(HFAA) ₃	20.1	19.95	24.1	23.91		
9.	Ho(HFAA) ₃	21.5	21.49	23.6	23.45		
10.	Er(HFAA) ₃	21.9	21.71	23.5	23.38		
11.	Pr(BZTFA) ₃	17.7	17.91	45.6	45.82	1400	1800
12.	Nd(BZTFA) ₃	18.1	18.24	45.4	45.57	(1.75)	(2.25)
13.	Sm(BZTFA) ₃	18.7	18.86	45.0	45.22		
14.	Ho(BZTFA) ₃	20.2	20.32	44.3	44.41		
15.	Er(BZTFA) ₃	20.4	20.54	44.1	44.28		
16.	Pr(PFBZA) ₃	14.1	14.04	36.1	35.91		
17.	Nd(PFBZA) ₃	14.5	14.35	35.9	35.79		
18.	Sm(PFBZA) ₃	15.0	14.85	35.7	35.57		
19.	Ho(PFBZA) ₃	16.5	16.65	35.2	35.07		
20.	Er(PFBZA) ₃	16.2	16.24	35.3	34.99		

Results and Discussion

Molecular weight determination of these chelates by cryoscopic method in benzene indicated them to be dimeric (2 to 2.2). But ebullioscopic method in refluxing benzene have shown them to have lower complexity around 1.8. The lower complexity of the chelates in refluxing benzene may most probably be due to partial ionization of the chelate in refluxing benzene.

The introduction of fluorine in the diketone pushes the C—O and C—C stretching to higher region⁷. The most intense band in these chelates is the C—O band occurring around 1610-1630 cm^{-1} region while C—C band occurs as the second intense band between 1520-38 cm^{-1} region. Both these bands have been found to shift at lower frequency as compared to the ligand. Bands occurring in the region 1200-600 cm^{-1} are due to intermixing and overlapping of bands and hence difficult to assign.

The metal ligand vibrations appear below 500 cm^{-1} while the region below 500 cm^{-1} is clear in the ligand. This region provides information on the strength of M—O bond and hence gives an idea of the comparative stability of the complexes⁸. Three bands in each of these chelates in the 410-434, 375-385; 275-295 region have been observed. The comparison of force constants (Table 2) of the three (M—O) bands indicated that the strength of M—O bond increases with the increase in the fluorine substitution. Comparing the force constants of the (M—O) band in the chelates of the same ligand, it was observed that the strength of the M—O bond increases with the atomic number of lanthanide.

Absorption: Absorption spectra of lanthanides have been a subject of several investigations⁹⁻¹². The presence of electrons in the '4f' orbital may invoke some electron delocalization from the metal to the antibonding molecular orbital of the ligand. Karraker¹² showed that the symmetry coordination number of lanthanide ion could be predicted from the shape, intensity and wavelength of the hypersensitive transition in the visible region. The shape of hypersensitive transition of Nd(TFAA)₃·2H₂O and Nd(HFAA)₃·2H₂O in benzene solution was quite similar to the octacoordinated species. The similarity among the spectra indicated that in solution atleast, the dihydrated tris chelates have octacoordinated stereochemistry. It is of course risky to transfer conclusions from the solution measurements to the solid compounds, but we feel the evidence in hand suggests that these dihydrate tris chelates are most probably octacoordinated in solid state as well. The shape of hypersensitive transition of anhydrous neodymium chelate is different from the dihydrated analogue, indicating thereby that during dehydration the coordination sphere of neodymium ion changes.

Taking free ion as standard, ligands other than fluoride cause red shift of the band¹³. The magnitude of red shift (nephelauxetic effect) depends upon the change in the interelectronic repulsion parameter. The nephelauxetic ratio (β), covalency parameter (δ)¹³ and bonding parameter ($b^{\frac{1}{2}}$)¹³ of these chelates have been calculated from the electronic spectra and the results are summarized in Table 2. The positive values of covalency parameter and bonding parameter suggest the incidence of some covalent character in the metal ligand bond. The absolute values of these parameters are

NOTES

TABLE 2—IR AND ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA

Sl. No.	Complex	ν M—O I	ν M—O II	ν M—O III	Average β	Average δ	Average $b\frac{1}{2}$
1.	Pr(TFAA) ₃	412(ms)	375(m)	275(w)	0.9960	0.401	0.044
2.	Nd(TFAA) ₃	412(ms)	375(m)	277(w)	0.9956	0.467	0.047
3.	Sm(TFAA) ₃	414(m)	276(m)	277(w)	0.9949	0.512	0.050
4.	Ho(TFAA) ₃	415(m)	378(m)	277(w)	0.9917	0.836	0.064
5.	Er(TFAA) ₃	417(m)	380(m)	278(w)	0.9896	1.050	0.072
6.	Pr(HFAA) ₃	418(ms)	379(m)	280(w)	0.9938	0.623	0.055
7.	Nd(HFAA) ₃	420(ms)	383(m)	280(w)	0.9953	0.472	0.049
8.	Sm(HFAA) ₃	420(ms)	383(m)	281(w)	0.9946	0.543	0.052
9.	Ho(HFAA) ₃	420(ms)	384(m)	282(w)	0.9905	0.959	0.068
10.	Er(HFAA) ₃	423(ms)	385(m)	284(w)	0.9987	1.142	0.075
11.	Pr(BZTFA) ₃	416(ms)	377(m)	278(w)	0.9937	0.634	0.055
12.	Nd(BZTFA) ₃	416(ms)	378(m)	279(w)	0.9949	0.513	0.050
13.	Sm(BZTFA) ₃	418(ms)	380(m)	280(w)	0.9934	0.553	0.057
14.	Ho(BZTFA) ₃	419(ms)	382(m)	281(w)	0.9913	0.877	0.066
15.	Er(BZTFA) ₃	422(ms)	382(ms)	285(w)	0.9900	1.010	0.070
16.	Pr(PFBZA) ₃	422(ms)	378(m)	279(w)	0.9953	0.472	0.049
17.	Nd(PFBZA) ₃	422(m)	380(m)	282(w)	0.9936	0.644	0.056
18.	Sm(PFBZA) ₃	424(m)	380(m)	283(w)	0.9944	0.563	0.053
19.	Ho(PFBZA) ₃	426(m)	382(m)	285(w)	0.9898	1.080	0.073
20.	Er(PFBZA) ₃	428(m)	384(m)	287(w)	0.9873	1.286	0.080

of little significance, yet these values are useful in a comparative study of the bonding in these complexes.

These anhydrous complexes have been found to dissolve in organic solvents. The molar conductance of these chelates in benzene ranges between 3.2-5.8 mho and in DMF 10.0-12.0 mho suggesting that they behave almost like non-electrolyte. The low degree of dissociation suggests that these are of inner sphere complexes.

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Polyamino Chelates of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Pd(II) using Cysteine as a Secondary Ligand

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A large number of studies on the interaction of transition metal ions with amino acids have been carried out because of their biological interest¹⁻⁵. They have also been studied in relation to the determination of their structure and formation constants using various physico-chemical methods. This information on the simple metal complexes of cysteine⁶⁻¹¹ are also available but a very little has been done on the mixed ligand complexes of this reagent¹²⁻¹⁴. The present investigation on ternary complexing system of bivalent metal ions involving dipyriddy and o-phenanthroline as primary and cysteine as secondary ligand, is an attempt to fill this gap.

Irving and Rossotti pH-titration technique¹⁵ as modified by Chidambaram and Bhattacharya¹⁶ has been used for the determination of stability constants. All the experiments were carried out at 24 ± 1° and at $\mu = 0.1M$ (NaClO₄) in aqueous

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